

Disparities in Health: Equity Aspects of Avoidable Mortality

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Abstract

Health inequity, that is socially determined, and preventable disparities in health, hinders the advancement of life expectancy. In Russia, which has witnessed the collapse of a social system rooted in the principles of social equality in a remarkably brief historical period, both the topic itself and the search for methods to investigate it are of utmost importance. The **purpose** of the study is to evaluate the manifestations of health inequity through the lens of their social dependence and preventability in terms of avoidable mortality.

Material and methods. The calculation of avoidable mortality is based on the cause classification in ages under 65, proposed by Walter W. Holland in 1993. The analysis was conducted using data for the period between 2000 and 2019. The subsequent period is marked by turbulence. The study used official data provided by Rosstat as its information base. Standardized mortality rates for preventable death causes were calculated using the direct method (European standard population).

Results. The disparity in life expectancy between urban and rural populations, as well as its regional variations, is largely attributable to avoidable mortality. The example of a substantial reduction in the rural-urban gap in avoidable mortality over the first two decades of the 21st century, including a convergence in treatable deaths, suggests that significant progress has been made in addressing health disparities between urban and rural populations within a remarkably short timeframe.

In terms of regional disparities, progress is minimal. The economically prosperous regions of the country have much greater potential for improving the life expectancy of their populations by reducing preventable deaths, compared to poorer regions. In both cases, priority should be given to prevention interventions aimed at lifestyle modification, as the social component of avoidable mortality dominates, and interventions aimed at reducing it are the most cost-effective strategy.

Keywords

health inequality; health inequity, avoidable mortality; preventable death causes; death causes as markers of health care availability and quality

JEL codes: I14

Introduction

Health inequality refers to any measurable aspects of health that vary among different people, i.e. there are no moral judgments in this term about whether the observed differences are fair (Kawachi et al. 2002).

The disparities between age groups are not unfair when older people die more often than younger (Arcaya et al. 2015). Furthermore, most disparities in health of different people are attributed to random factors (Smith 2011). That is, some level of inequality in health is objective.

If disparities in the health status of population groups living within the same area or country are systematic, persist over a long period of time and become more pronounced, then they are amenable to change and must be eliminated (Krieger 2012). That is, inequality in health is useful to analyze not in a general sense but only to identify unjust differences where the problem of social injustice arises. In English, a different term is used for health inequality in this sense – “health inequity” (McCartney et al. 2019). It is precisely health inequity, which can be addressed and eliminated, that should be a priority for public health promotion programs in addressing the challenge of increasing overall life expectancy. Accordingly, we will continue to analyze health disparities using the English-language term “health inequity”, even though it is often translated as “health inequality” in Russian.

A literature review conducted by O.A. Kislitsyna identified three main hypotheses explaining socio-economic inequality in health. The first hypothesis, based on social selection theory, suggests that health determines a person’s social and economic status. The second hypothesis, known as the social causation hypothesis, argues that social and economic status affects health through intermediate factors such as material, psychosocial, and behavioral factors. The third hypothesis, called the life journey hypothesis, suggests that differences in adult health can be partially explained by social and economic factors experienced during early development (Kislitsyna 2017).

The assessment of social inequality in terms of the life cycle is based on the understanding that different types of factors contribute to social inequality at different stages of life. These factors can include those that affect the intrauterine period, such as fetal growth retardation, premature birth, and congenital malformations. These conditions are more likely to occur in children born to mothers with low education levels and social and economic status (Mortensen et al. 2009). Neglect in childhood can lead to low self-esteem, increased risk of behavioral problems, depression, and decreased stress tolerance later in life. Children from families with limited resources are more likely to experience problems during early development (Yanos et al. 2010).

Economic research has demonstrated that investments in children’s intellectual and social development in their early years have a far greater influence on their health and economic prospects than those made later in life (Conti and Heckman 2010). It is evident that a prosperous childhood, including intrauterine development of a child, serves as the foundation for their health, extending into adulthood.

The next stage of a child’s development has a significant impact on their education, and subsequently on their chances in the job market. These chances are lower for individuals with health issues and those who lack sufficient education. According to the first hypothesis, social factors play a role in this process, as poor health can hinder the pursuit of a high-quality education or lucrative employment. There is a strong relationship between the parental social status and the academic success of their children, especially in terms of their edu-

cational attainment. The education of the mother has a significant influence on the child's future prospects (Davis-Kean et al. 2021). Habits that are formed at an early age can have a significant impact on a person's future health choices (Fasang and Mayer 2020). During the school years and adolescence, health disparities formed in early childhood become more pronounced.

Depending on the social status of adults in society, they may be exposed to different levels of risk factors due to their work, living conditions, and physical environment. Poor health, especially psychological problems, can increase the risk of unemployment (Bartley et al. 2006).

The relationship between income and mortality reflects the cumulative effect of a long causal chain in which social background and early development affect both income and health through their effects on health, employment and work environment, on the development of health problems and their solution, but the disease and its consequences for employment affect income (Galobardes et al. 2006). According to experts, addressing the root causes of health inequity requires breaking the cycle of poverty that leads to diseases leading to poverty – “a 21st century health poverty trap” (Bor et al. 2017).

In the Russian scientific literature, the topic of inequity in health is not very popular. In the Soviet period – for ideological reasons, because of setting the goal of achieving social homogeneity of society and “erasing differences” in terms of social, professional, educational, ethnic, residence-dependent and other features. In the post-Soviet period, against the background of significant social and economic polarization of society and an obvious increase in disparities in health and mortality, research on this topic for a long time was practically suppressed as a result of the adoption of the Federal Law “On civil status acts” No 143-03 dated November 15, 1997. According to this law, all social and economic characteristics of the deceased were excluded from the primary accounting and reporting documents.

However, a number of studies based on population censuses, found significant differences in adult mortality during the Soviet period by level of education and type of employment (Andreev and Dobrovolskaya 1993; Inequality and mortality in Russia 2000; Andreev et al. 2005a). In the post-Soviet period, the topic was further developed. For example, studies conducted over a period of available data have shown that during the first half of the 1990s – an unprecedented rise in peace-time mortality – the increase among well-educated men over 30 was twice as low as the general population of this age, while there was no increase in mortality among their educated female peers (Andreev et al. 2005b). The educational mortality factor has been confirmed to be important in explaining the variation in the level and causes of death, not only among the adult population (Ivanova et al. 2014), but also in infant mortality (Andreev and Kvasha 2005).

However, the majority of studies focus on the analysis of regional differences in mortality, which can be explained by the vast territory of Russia, diversity of natural, socio-economic, cultural and ethnic conditions. In the Soviet era, it was found that there is a “northeastern gradient of mortality” in Russia (Andreev 1979; Shkolnikov 1987). This phenomenon has remained stable for almost six decades and is still relevant today (Starodubov et al. 2003; Demographic development of Russia in the 21st century 2009; Demographic present and future of Russia 2012; Razvitie chelovecheskogo potentsiala v Rossii skvoz' prizmu zdorov'ya naseleniya 2012; Rybakovsky and Kozhevnikova 2015; Timonin et al. 2017; Danilova 2018; Rodionova and Kopnova 2020). As a general rule, the northeastern mortality gradient is explained by the level of “favorable living conditions”. This refers primarily to the overall level of development of the area and favorable natural and climatic conditions.

Inequities in health are manifested through different levels of morbidity and mortality within one country, region or city. Many diseases can act as markers of a social gradient of health. The toolkit proposed as part of the concept of avoidable mortality seems to be effective. This approach identifies a group of causes that can be prevented in the context of modern advancements in medicine, healthcare, and social sector and, therefore, are excessive. There are two categories of causes: treatable and preventable. The prevention of deaths that are caused by treatable causes depends on timely and accurate diagnosis, as well as quality treatment. Deaths due to preventable causes can be prevented through public health interventions that address broader determinants of health, such as behaviors, lifestyles, socio-economic factors (such as living conditions and standard of living), and environmental factors (Nolte and McKee 2004).

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the manifestations of health inequity through the lens of their social dependence and preventability in terms of avoidable mortality.

Material and methods

Mortality is not the only indicator of health. Simultaneously, with a relatively low life expectancy (with clear success in reducing mortality after 2004, this is precisely the case in Russia), mortality rates can accurately reflect the health of the population. The issue of finding additional health indicators beyond mortality is becoming more acute in developed countries, with a significant increase in the number of older people and the length of their lives. So far, the main source of life expectancy growth in Russia has been a reduction in premature mortality at working age with a very little increase in the lifespan of the elderly population.

The disparities in avoidable mortality are examined in relation to the place of residence, urban or rural area. This approach is informed by the well-documented disparities in mortality between rural and urban areas, as well as between different regions of Russia. These disparities are not limited to our country; they are global, albeit with varying degrees of magnitude and focus.

The age under 65 is considered a reasonable period for prevention in Russia, given the current level of development. However, for developed countries with life expectancy above 80 years, it rises to 75 years. The age range up to 65 is most relevant as it encompasses the period of childhood and working age, i.e. the interval within which determinants of inequities in health are formed and implemented.

Since these are circumstances of a fundamental nature, the analysis is based on the 2019 data. The situation in the subsequent period is turbulent due to the crisis associated with the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020-2021 and the geopolitical risks the country has been facing since 2022. The analysis of regional differences for one year does not affect the sustainability of results. The period up to 2020 was characterized by sustained positive trends, against the background of which regional differences in mortality began to decrease slightly. The traditional geographic patterns of prosperity – disadvantage remained unchanged.

The calculation of avoidable mortality is based on the cause classification in aged under 65, proposed by Walter W. Holland in 1993 (Holland 1993). Although there are more current versions of the list of preventable causes, it was considered advisable to use an earlier version given the mortality rates in Russia and significant reserves of reducing mortality precisely from preventable causes.

Mortality classified as preventable includes 38 causes, groups and classes of causes, divided into three main groups according to the three levels of prevention (Table 1).

The first group includes causes of death that can be prevented through primary prevention. This group includes causes largely determined by lifestyle, mainly what are commonly called bad habits, the most important of which is alcohol and tobacco consumption (vascular disorders of the brain, malignant neoplasms of the upper digestive and respiratory tracts, lungs, bladder, and liver) and other conditions associated with alcohol consumption (chronic diseases of the liver). In addition, some of malignant neoplasms in this group may also be defined by occupational risk factors (lungs, bladder, liver). The first group also includes injury and poisoning which, in addition to behavioral factors, are significantly influenced by law enforcement, socio-economic and social factors such as road safety (speed limits, use of safety belts, etc.) and crime control.

The second group refers to causes eligible for secondary prevention, i.e. timely detection and early diagnosis. This group includes, primarily, breast and cervix uterine malignant neoplasms, as well as melanoma. Other malignant neoplasms of the uterus are also included in this group, because inaccurate coding and poor diagnosis make it difficult to separate these causes from malignant neoplasms of the uterus.

The third group includes causes associated with improvements in quality of treatment and care. Vaccination and treatment are largely related to deaths from infectious diseases, although factors such as clean water and healthy diet should not be underestimated. Changes in mortality from other causes in this group requiring medical and surgical intervention (hypertension, ulcers, complications of pregnancy, appendicitis, hernia, cholelithiasis) are related to the set of measures and coordination of different health services, such as emergency services, adequate medical care and surgery, etc.

For ease of analysis, the second and third groups of causes are combined into a group caused by medical or health factors. The first group is attributed to social factors.

Table 1. Causes of avoidable mortality in people aged under age 65

Death causes and classes of causes	ICD-10 codes
1 group	
Malignant neoplasms of lip, cavity and pharynx	C00-C14
Malignant neoplasm of esophagus	C15
Malignant neoplasm of liver and intrahepatic bile ducts	C22
Malignant neoplasm of larynx	C32
Malignant neoplasm of trachea, bronchus and lung	C33, C34
Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined sites in the respiratory system and intrathoracic organs	C30, C31, C37-C39
Malignant neoplasm of bladder	C67
Malignant neoplasms of other and unspecified urinary organs	C65, C66, C68
Nontraumatic subarachnoid hemorrhage	I60
Nontraumatic intracranial hemorrhage	I61-I62
Cerebral infarction	I63
Stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction	I64

Death causes and classes of causes	ICD-10 codes
Other cerebrovascular diseases	I67-I69
Alcoholic liver disease (alcoholic cirrhosis of liver, hepatitis, fibrosis)	K70
Fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver (not alcohol-related)	K74
Other liver diseases	K71-K73, K75-K76
Chapter XIX. Injury, poisoning and certain other consequences of external causes	S00-S09, T00-T98
2 group	
Malignant melanoma of skin	C43
Other malignant neoplasms of skin	C44
Malignant neoplasm of breast	C50
Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri	C53
Malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified parts of uterus	C54, C55
3 group	
Malignant neoplasm of prostate	C61
Malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified male genital	C60, C62, C63
Hodgkin lymphoma	C81
Other non-Hodgkin lymphoma	C82-C85
Leukemia	C91-C95
Chronic rheumatic heart diseases	I05-I09
Hypertensive diseases	I11- I13, I10, I15
Gastric ulcer	K25
Duodenal ulcer	K26
Diseases of appendix	K35-K38
Hernia	K40-K46
Cholelithiasis	K80
Cholecystitis	K81
Chapter I. Certain infectious and parasitic diseases	A00-A99, B00-B99
Chapter X. Diseases of the respiratory system	J00-J99
Chapter XV. Pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium	O00-O99

The information basis for the study was the official statistics provided by Rosstat, on death distribution by place of residence, gender, age, and cause of death as well as data on the average annual population of urban and rural areas by gender and age, for both Russia as a whole for the years 2000 to 2019 and for each constituent entity of the Russian Federation in 2019. Furthermore, data on life expectancy for urban and rural populations was obtained from the EMISS Rosstat system.

To calculate the standardized mortality rates for preventable causes of death, the direct method was employed, using the European Standard Population¹.

1 The Demographic Yearbook of Russia (2023) Section 6 Methodical notes. URL: https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/Dem_ejegod_2023.htm

Results

Rural-urban disparities

In Russia as a whole, the rural life expectancy is chronically lower than the urban one (Fig. 1). However, there are 14 exceptions to this trend. The exception group is represented by regions with a low rural population (for example, the Murmansk region), whose indicators are unstable due to their small size, and, conversely, by regions with the highest rural proportion (for example, the Republic of Crimea, the Krasnodar region, the Chechen Republic, Ingushetia, Karachay-Cherkessia), where living conditions in rural areas are more favorable and relieved from the risks associated with urban areas.

The disparity in life expectancy between rural and urban areas is not constant. We can observe a consistent rise in this disparity in the 2000s: from 2001 to 2009, the gap increased from 0.9 to 2.8 years in males and from 0.7 to 2.1 years in females followed by a similarly steady decline in the disparity between rural and urban residents: in 2019, it equaled to 1.4 and 1.2 years, i.e. it halved (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics in average life expectancy in Russia, 2000-2019

At first glance, the maximum equity of urban and rural residents was observed in 2000-2001, with the urban gain of less than 1 year in males and 0.7 years in females, but it should not be forgotten that this was a kind of equity “in poverty” (during this period the life expectancy among the Russian urban and rural populations continued to decline due to the negative consequences of the 1998 default). The current reduction in urban and rural disparities is observed against the background of rising life expectancy. In 2019, life expectancy equaled to 68.7 years in urban females and 78.4 years in urban males, and 67.3 and 77.2 years in rural females and males, respectively – the highest figures in the history of Russia. The convergence of urban and rural life expectancy in the 2000s, which was 9.3 years versus 8.9 years in males and 5.9 years versus 5.4 years in females, due to developments over the last decade, is particularly noteworthy. In the 2000s, rural areas lagged significantly behind the urban areas in terms of growth rate of life expectancy (2.4 versus 4.3 years in males and 1.4 versus 2.9 years in females), in 2010-2019, rural areas were significantly ahead of the urban areas

by this indicator (6.2 years and 3.8 years in urban areas against 4.9 years and 3 years in rural areas, respectively).

It should be noted that in males, these changes are entirely due to trends in avoidable mortality, which depends on both lifestyle and living conditions (social component) and healthcare performance (medical component). In 2000-2010. The rate of positive trends in avoidable mortality in urban population exceeded the one in rural population, standing at 31.7% versus 20.9% (social component) and 26.8% versus 25.6% (medical component). In 2010-2019, the situation changed dramatically: mortality from preventable causes in rural population decreased by 38.9%, while mortality from treatable causes reduced by 36.1% compared to a 33.7% and 29.2% reduction in urban population, respectively (Fig. 2-3).

Figure 2. Dynamics in mortality from preventable causes (social factors) among the Russian population aged under 65, 2000-2019 (standardized ratio per 100.000 population).

Figure 3. Dynamics in mortality from treatable causes (medical factors) among the Russian population aged under 65, 2000-2019 (standardized ratio per 100.000 population).

In females, the situation was similar, with one exception: already in 2000-2010, the rate of reduction in treatable causes of avoidable mortality among rural females was higher compared to their urban peers (16.2% versus 14.1%), while urban females had a higher rate of decline in mortality from preventable causes (social factors) (27.8% versus 14.5%), in 2010-2019, rural females had higher indicators of mortality reduction from both preventable causes and treatable causes (a 21.2% and 41.2% reduction versus 17.6% and 33.4%, respectively) (Fig. 2-3).

As a result of this trend in the 2000s, the rate of decline in urban mortality from preventable causes hardly outperformed the one in rural population (54.7% and 51.9% in males and females compared to 51.7% and 49.7% respectively), while mortality from treatable causes declined at a higher rate in rural population compared to urban population (52.5% and 34% in males and females versus 48.1% and 29.2%, respectively).

It should be noted that higher disparity in mortality from preventable causes in rural population was observed throughout the study period, but by 2019 it had decreased to 18.6% in males and 22.5% in females compared to 29.8% and 38.8% at the end of the 2000s, when the disparities were maximum.

It is extremely interesting that avoidable mortality from treatable causes in urban and rural populations has almost equalized in recent years, with the difference in both sexes not exceeding 5% compared to 17.5% and 13.0% in 2009, respectively.

Regional disparities

Analyzing the disparities in life expectancy across Russian regions, we observe that in 2019, they reached 14.8 years in males and 9.4 years females. These disparities, particularly in males, are equivalent to a whole epidemiological era.

Two sustainable vectors remain relevant: the prosperous European South – disadvantaged North and the prosperous European West – disadvantaged Asian East.

However, when discussing the prosperous areal, it is worth noting that, in addition to the national republics of the North Caucasus and the southern Russian territories, the prosperous areal includes both capitals, the Moscow region, the Leningrad region, as well as the Khanty-Mansi autonomous district and the Yamalo-Nenets autonomous district, located far to the north in the Circumpolar Urals and Polar Urals.

The disadvantaged areal is shaped by the East Siberian and Far Eastern regions, as well as the European North, particularly the Pskov and Novgorod regions, which share a border with the prosperous Leningrad region.

In the context of avoidable mortality, it is important to highlight the significant disparities across regions. In terms of mortality from preventable causes, the disparity between males and females is as high as 4.4 times, and 7.1 times, respectively. When it comes to mortality from treatable causes, the gap is even greater adding up to 5.1 times in both sexes.

Furthermore, it is important to highlight that all prosperous and disadvantaged regions in terms of life expectancy, as a rule, were characterized by low and high rates of mortality from preventable causes, respectively. However, as to mortality from treatable causes, this condition was not mandatory (Table 2). Within the prosperous areal, males in Sevastopol, Karachay-Cherkessia, North Ossetia, Adygea, as well as the Volgograd and Rostov regions and females in Adygea and St. Petersburg (which is surprising, in our view), the rates of mortality from treatable causes turned out to be average.

Table 2. Distribution of the Russian regions by life expectancy, avoidable mortality from preventable causes and treatable causes, 2019.

Indicators	low	average	high
Males			
Life expectancy (years)	<65.6	65.5–68.4	>68.5
Avoidable mortality from preventable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)	<255.0	254.9–324.9	>325.0
Avoidable mortality from treatable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)	<64.5	64.6–89.9	>90
Females			
Life expectancy (years)	<76.6	76.5–78.4	>78.5
Avoidable mortality from preventable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)	<62.0	61.9–89.9	>90.0
Avoidable mortality from treatable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)	<39.0	38.9–57.4	>57.5

On the other hand, mortality from treatable causes turned out to be average in regions with low life expectancy: in population of the republics of Karelia and Komi, as well as the Pskov region, in males in the republics of Altai and Buryatia, the Kamchatka Territory and the Sakhalin region, and in females in Khakassia, the Khabarovsk Territory, the Novgorod and Amur regions – advancements in medicine failed to compensate for the social problems of these regions.

Third, there is no clear relationship between the level of economic development in regions and the rate of avoidable mortality. In fact, expecting such a relationship is based on the widely accepted idea that there is a close correlation between the level of economic development and life expectancy in countries. However, “at the regional level in Russia, this correlation was practically non-existent both during the economic crisis in the late 1990s and significant regional disparities (Zdorov’e naseleniya Rossii v social’nom kontekste 90-kh godov: problemy i perspektivy 2003) and the period of economic growth at the end of the first decade of the new century (Andreev and Shkolnikov 2018; Human potential development in Russia through the prism of public health 2012). Likewise, this correlation is not present even a decade later, in the present day” (Ivanova 2022).

From the point of view of the analysis of avoidable mortality, it is important to analyze the causes of the disparities, which are of a chronic nature (Appendix).

Consequently, in the group with GRP that is 1.5 times or more higher than the national average, there is a concentration of areas with markedly different levels of avoidable mortality. On the one hand, Moscow and St. Petersburg stand out as leaders in terms of socio-economic progress and human capital development, including their lower rates of avoidable mortality compared to the national average (1.8 and 1.4 times in males, and 1.5 and 1.2 times in females, respectively). On the other hand, the Khanty-Mansi and Yamalo-Nenets autonomous districts have high economic potential, yet they face challenges in developing their social infrastructure. Despite some successes in this area, that have led to a substitution reduction in mortality rates, including preventable deaths (1.3 times lower than the national average in males and 1.2 times in females, respectively), some problems still remain. In all

other regions of this group, where GRP is 1.5 times or more compared to the national average, avoidable mortality is higher than the national average, including 1.6 times and 1.8 times higher in males in the Magadan region and the Chukotka autonomous district, and 1.5 times and 2.3 times higher in females, respectively.

At the other end of the spectrum, in the group of regions with GRP twice and more lower than the national average, there is also a significant disparity in avoidable mortality. It is worth noting that the republics of the North Caucasus, where the average per capita GRP is three times lower than the national average, have achieved a remarkable reduction in avoidable mortality, bringing the rate down to levels that are 1.5 to 2 times lower than the national average. However, if we exclude these republics with obviously unreliable mortality statistics, the remaining regions can be divided into two groups: the first group with avoidable mortality higher than the national average, including ultra-high, being 1.5 to 1.9 times higher in males and 1.7 to 2.4 times higher females: the Trans-Baikal Territory, the Kurgan region, the Republic of Tyva, and the second group of regions with indicators that are relatively close to the Russian average ($\pm 10\%$ range) and even lower than the national average: the Tambov region, the republics of Mordovia and Kalmykia, and Stavropol Territory and Sevastopol.

Some other groups of regions deserve separate consideration due to clear contradictions between their average per capita GRP and rates of avoidable mortality. On the one hand, these are the Murmansk region, the Komi Republic, and the Kamchatka Territory, where higher than average economic potential is not being fully realized in terms of reducing avoidable mortality, which remains high by Russian standards. On the other hand, this is a larger group of regions with lower per capita GRPs than the national average, yet they have managed to reduce avoidable mortality closer to the national average level.

To substantiate strategies aimed at reducing mortality, it is crucial to comprehend the key concerns. The key concerns are evaluated by comparing the avoidable mortality rate in the region (preventable causes and treatable causes separately) with the national average.

Let us examine the group of regions where per capita GRP is 1.5 times or more higher than the national average. In regions with economic potential being realized to reduce avoidable mortality, such as Moscow, St. Petersburg, the Khanty-Mansi autonomous district, and the Yamalo-Nenets autonomous district, the reduction is achieved through both primary prevention and lifestyle improvements, as well as through healthcare initiatives. In regions, where high per capita GRP is accompanied by high avoidable mortality, the need for lifestyle improvements is a pressing issue, as preventable causes of avoidable mortality (social component) significantly exceed the national average, while treatable causes (medical component) are relatively lower. However, in the case of the Chukotka autonomous district, the medical component is more prominent.

Let us examine the group of regions where per capita GRP is half the national average. Within this group with low avoidable mortality, the social component, such as minimizing deaths associated with behavioral factors, is an absolute priority. However, there is an exception – Sevastopol and the republics of the North Caucasus, where the focus is on the medical component, specifically reducing mortality through effective healthcare performance, such as timely diagnosis and high-quality treatment. In the sub-group with the level of avoidable mortality close to the national average, the effect is achieved through a balanced use of prevention and medical interventions, resulting in roughly equal importance of the social and medical components of avoidable mortality (as the ratio of regional and national average levels). In regions with low economic potential and high rates of avoidable mortality, its de-

cline reserves are related to both social and medical components (preventable and treatable causes), but priority is given to prevention efforts, not only because deaths from preventable causes exceed the national average, but also due to the fact that prevention is a more cost-effective strategy, especially in the context of limited resources.

Reserves of avoidable mortality reduction: a regional perspective

When assessing possible reserves for reducing avoidable mortality, it is essential to consider not only the economic potential of a region, but also its geographical location. Therefore, it would be appropriate to analyze the situation with due regard to these factors, shifting the situation analysis in each region from the federal level to that of large regions such as federal districts. It is more productive to assess the potential of the regions-outsiders not only in comparison with the indicators of the district leader, but also the average district indicators (Table 3).

Table 3. Variation in avoidable mortality from preventable causes and treatable causes in the federal districts of the Russian Federation (standardized ratio per 100.000 population), 2019.

	Avoidable mortality from preventable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)		Avoidable mortality from treatable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)	
	males	females	males	females
Russia				
minimum	113.1	35.0	30.0	27.6
maximum	497.2	212.4	177.2	141.4
average	257.8	75.8	75.8	47.8
Central Federal District				
minimum	142.1	42.0	36.0	27.6
maximum	333.7	89.8	92.6	63.8
average	222.0	59.4	53.9	38.7
North-Western Federal District				
minimum	180.8	53.2	52.6	40.2
maximum	363.8	109.2	97.4	53.6
average	261.2	75.0	67.6	46.9
Southern Federal District				
minimum	209.0	58.7	43.4	27.9
maximum	230.4	70.0	96.0	59.8
average	257.8	62.1	72.8	45.1
North Caucasian Federal District				
minimum	113.1	30.0	35.0	32.2
maximum	218.0	59.6	67.8	43.8
average	150.2	39.1	45.5	34.2

	Avoidable mortality from preventable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)		Avoidable mortality from treatable causes (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)	
	males	females	males	females
Volga Federal District				
minimum	220.6	53.4	42.6	32.5
maximum	335.3	89.0	109.5	64.1
average	285.5	75.8	80.6	46.8
Ural Federal District				
minimum	195.6	48.8	50.7	33.1
maximum	355.7	83.5	130.1	66.0
average	282.0	73	96.1	56.5
Siberian Federal District				
minimum	259.6	74.0	79.8	33.5
maximum	497.2	212.4	177.2	69.1
average	306.2	89.6	125.5	93.0
Far Eastern Federal District				
minimum	305.0	78.6	60.2	39.2
maximum	467.8	155.2	147.6	141.4
average	372.5	112.6	95.9	61.1

The assessment of the situation in the Central Federal District is the least revealing according to these criteria, as the average indicators for the district are heavily influenced by Moscow due to its size. However, even in the Central District, when compared with the average district indicators, the gap between the outsiders and the leader (Moscow) is narrowed. In this context, the disparity in avoidable mortality is reduced from more than two to 1.5 times in terms of deaths from preventable causes, and up to 70% to 60% in terms of treatable causes.

A comparable proportion is seen across all eight federal districts (Table 3). The Ural Federal District stands out in this regard: the challenge for the Kurgan region, the district outsider, is to narrow the disparity in avoidable mortality by 26.1% and 14.4% in terms of deaths from preventable causes rather than 2-fold, and by 35.4% and 16.8% in terms of deaths from treatable causes, which seems quite achievable.

Discussion

When discussing the issues of health equality and equity in Russia, the issue of equality and inequality is quantitative and rather declarative. The problem of equity is much more complex: at first glance, it may seem fair to address the noted lag in some of the most important indicators in the country. However, this approach is unlikely to be feasible, so the purpose of this study is to determine whether this inequity is objectively substantiated and therefore fair in the current context.

Discussing the disparities in health between urban and rural populations, it is important to acknowledge that these disparities are common throughout the modern world, yet they are not universally applicable. In this context, the narrowing gap in life expectancy between rural and urban populations in Russia, observed in the 2000s, is a positive development. Furthermore, it is crucial to consider that the convergence in life expectancy between urban and rural populations is primarily driven by trends in avoidable mortality, which are more favorable among rural population. This has resulted in a substantial reduction in the disparity in mortality from preventable causes, and in almost eliminated disparity in mortality from treatable causes.

It can thus be stated that, despite the continuing gap in life expectancy between rural and urban populations, there is a gradual minimization of this inequity, determined by both preventable causes and treatable causes of avoidable mortality.

What are the drivers of such dramatic changes in health inequity between urban and rural populations?

Probably, two groups of factors can be distinguished. The first and, in our view, most important is investment in agriculture to ensure food security of the country. This not only created jobs with decent pay, but in general led to the development of rural areas, renovation and creation of new infrastructure. Not all regions in the country are affected by these processes, but overall at the national level the positive dynamics cannot be denied. The second group of factors is related to the implementation of the program of modernization of the primary health care, which has primarily benefited the rural health care by building and equipping feldsher-midwife stations, medical outpatient clinics, developing the system of mobile diagnostics, etc.

The disparities in health across regions are less encouraging. In 2019, the disparity in life expectancy between males and females added up to 14.8 years and 9.4 years, respectively. Despite positive trends in life expectancy in the country, these disparities remained almost unchanged. The geographic vector of mortality distribution remains consistent.

In this context, there is a possibility of a “geographical curse”, which would imply the existence of an objective disparity in life expectancy. Furthermore, efforts to identify a relationship between the level of economic development and life expectancy in Russia, as determined by international comparisons, have failed. While in the 1990s, the lack of this relationship could be attributed to the social and economic transformations in the country, after nearly three decades, a more plausible explanation is required.

If we exclude the regions where, probably because of unreliable data, there is a reverse relationship between the living standards and life expectancy, it can be said that a significant number of economically prosperous regions have much greater untapped life expectancy reserves compared to poor regions. It is not a question of geography, but rather of targeting economic potential for social development. Such antipodes are, for example, the Khanty-Mansi autonomous district and the Yamalo-Nenets autonomous district on the one hand, and the Krasnoyarsk Territory, the Sakhalin region and especially the Magadan region and the Chukotka autonomous district on the other hand. At the same time, in the group of regions with low economic potential, there are regions with high life expectancy. Again, one cannot ignore the geographical factor. Among the mentioned regions, there is not a single one located in harsh climatic and geographical conditions, by contrast, it is mostly the south of Central Russia and the Volga region.

The goal of developing a comprehensive mortality reduction strategy is closely linked to the issue of reducing inequity.

In regions with high avoidable mortality, regardless of their level of economic development, both the social and medical components (preventable causes of death and treatable causes of death) are problematic. However, in most cases, the priority is given to prevention interventions, both due to greater significance of the social component and higher cost-effectiveness of such measures.

With avoidable mortality rates close to the national average, priorities often depend on the economic potential of a region. In regions with higher economic opportunities, prevention interventions are also a priority, given a relatively favorable situation with treatable causes of avoidable mortality. However, in regions with lower economic potential, there is more variability, and priorities are determined by social policies in the region, such as a focus on prestigious facilities at the expense of social infrastructure or the prevention of marginalization.

At low levels of avoidable mortality, both components are usually balanced as a result of the motivation of people towards self-preservation behavior and effective healthcare.

Conclusion

Avoidable mortality prevented by lifestyle interventions and effective health care contributes significantly to the disparities in life expectancy between urban and rural populations, as well as its interregional variation. This makes it possible to mark such disparities as preventable and, therefore, unequitable.

Considering a substantial reduction in rural-urban disparities in avoidable mortality over the first two decades of the 21st century, including a convergence of mortality rates from treatable causes, it is evident that substantial progress has been achieved in eliminating health inequity between urban and rural populations within a remarkably short timeframe.

Russia is characterized by a significant disparity in health across different regions, as evidenced by a difference in life expectancy of 14.8 years in males and 9.4 years in females. This disparity remains largely unchanged despite positive trends at the national level. The absence of a relationship between the economic potential of a region, measured by GRP per capita, and the level of avoidable mortality highlights the inequity of these disparities.

Economically prosperous regions of the country have a more substantial unrealized potential for enhancing life expectancy by curbing avoidable mortality, compared to poor regions. In both cases, the imperative to refine public health policies is pressing, yet for poor regions, economic expansion is paramount, primarily to advance in reducing avoidable mortality. Conversely, for prosperous regions, the realization of economic growth is essential for social advancement. Priority in both cases is given to prevention interventions aimed at lifestyle modification, as the social component in avoidable mortality prevails, and efforts to reduce mortality from preventable causes are the most cost-effective strategy, as demonstrated by nations that have achieved high levels of life expectancy.

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Other sources of information

The Demographic Yearbook of Russia (2023) Section 6 Methodical notes. URL: https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/Dem_ejagod_2023.htm

Appendix

Table A1. Avoidable mortality in the Russian regions, 2019 (standardized ratio per 100.000 population)¹

	Per capita GRP	males			females		
		1	2	3	1	2	3
Russian Federation	647708	333.6	257.8	75.8	118.5	70.7	47.8
Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous District	5817780	274.5	223.8	50.7	100.7	67.6	33.1
Khanty-Mansiysk Autonomous District	2731118	259.9	195.6	64.3	86.1	48.8	37.3
Sakhalin Region	2397445	477.1	402.2	74.9	180.4	119.5	60.9
Chukotka Autonomous District	1900851	615.4	467.8	147.6	269.2	127.8	141.4
Moscow	1565396	185.6	142.1	43.5	77.5	42	35.5
Magadan Region	1524002	533.8	430.6	103.2	182.3	119.1	63.2
Republic of Sakha (Yakutia)	1266299	370.3	310.1	60.2	121.9	82.7	39.2
St. Petersburg	962002	235.2	180.8	54.4	98.3	53.2	45.1
Krasnoyarsk Region	939382	419.9	310.5	109.4	161.9	95.2	66.7
Kamchatka Territory	889982	376.4	305	71.4	141.5	78.6	62.9
Komi Republic	870098	438.9	363.8	75.1	158.5	109.2	49.3
Murmansk Region	827822	374.6	322	52.6	140.7	92.8	47.9
Tyumen Region (except fro Khanty-Mansi Autonomous District and Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous District)	808055	334.2	235.6	98.6	111	57.5	53.5
Republic of Tatarstan	720053	280.1	220.6	59.5	90.9	53.4	37.5
Moscow Region	679655	263.1	214.6	48.5	98.1	60.3	37.8
Leningrad Region	657232	380.1	293.9	86.2	135.9	84.2	51.7
Irkutsk Region	643246	467	330.8	136.2	177.7	90.7	87
Belgorod Region	617025	260.1	212.2	47.9	88.9	56	32.9
Khabarovsk Territory	610679	485.1	386.1	99	168.8	116.7	52.1
Astrakhan eRgion	595898	329.1	249.8	79.3	112.2	70.2	42
Sverdlovsk Region	587782	423.9	315.6	108.3	144.5	83.5	61
Perm Region	574428	434.8	325.3	109.5	153.1	89	64.1
Tomsk Region	573005	394.3	299.9	94.4	133.2	83.4	49.8
Orenburg Region	564477	390.7	288.4	102.3	143.9	82.8	61.1
Primorsky Territory	563015	442.1	329.2	112.9	171.7	100.4	71.3
Kaluga Region	546489	356.7	282.4	74.3	121.1	76.6	44.5
Vologda Region	543571	371.1	299	72.1	127.5	84.1	43.4

	Per capita GRP	males			females		
		1	2	3	1	2	3
Samara Region	531098	410.4	321.5	88.9	143.2	87.8	55.4
Republic of Karelia	517888	430.9	346.3	84.6	148.6	98	50.6
Kaliningrad Region	517151	311.8	246.5	65.3	120.9	71.3	49.6
Arkhangelsk Region	509848	377.1	315.2	61.9	123.6	83.4	40.2
Nizhny Novgorod Region	503983	375.1	295.7	79.4	120.4	77	43.4
Amur Region	499757	544.5	453	91.5	200.9	146.4	54.5
Lipetsk Region	499274	298.4	262.4	36	85.6	58	27.6
Yaroslavl Region	484799	371.3	301.4	69.9	120.7	80.8	39.9
Udmurt Republic	480561	397.1	321.5	75.6	129.9	87.6	42.3
Republic of Khakassia	478915	438.6	343.6	95	145.7	94.4	51.3
Novosibirsk Region	476753	380.6	259.6	121	137.6	74.2	63.4
Tula Region	459651	339.4	275.5	63.9	116.4	69.7	46.7
Novgorod Region	457565	458.5	361.1	97.4	151.8	104.2	47.6
Krasnodar Territory	455175	290	230.4	59.6	98.6	59.8	38.8
Kursk Region	448533	368.2	291.1	77.1	106.1	62.3	43.8
Republic of Bashkortostan	445862	359.8	265.1	94.7	122.1	73.4	48.7
Chelyabinsk Region	445834	393.8	297.1	96.7	141.7	77.8	63.9
Voronezh Region	430690	276.4	229.2	47.2	95.9	61	34.9
Kemerovo Region	416419	523.6	346.4	177.2	199	106	93
Omsk Region	398927	361.7	268.7	93	124.2	74	50.2
Vladimir Region	393135	396.7	333.7	63	126.3	85.3	41
Ryazan Region	392641	317.2	260.5	56.7	92.9	60.8	32.1
Rostov Region	389521	289	209	80	110.4	60.2	50.2
Tver Region	386059	387.5	294.9	92.6	149.7	85.9	63.8
Volgograd Region	385398	307.3	237	70.3	104.5	62.8	41.7
Smolensk Region	372073	382.5	305.3	77.2	137.4	89.8	47.6
Orel Region	362066	329.3	267.4	61.9	103.6	67	36.6
Jewish Autonomous District	357287	514.9	383.7	131.2	224	155.2	68.8
Tambov region	349773	294.2	250.6	43.6	91.4	58.7	32.7
Trans-Baikal Territory	347663	529.3	409	120.3	196	125.2	70.8
Ulyanovsk Region	344371	355	275.5	79.5	126.3	78	48.3
Penza Region	341904	365.4	305.4	60	105.1	72.5	32.6
Bryansk Region	333613	405	320.8	84.2	115.6	71.7	43.9
Saratov Region	333075	353.1	279.7	73.4	124.7	73.1	51.6
Republic of Mordovia	331412	285.9	243.3	42.6	89.6	54.8	34.8
Republic of Kalmykia	327289	299	255.6	43.4	86.6	58.7	27.9
Kostroma Region	320814	350.8	291.7	59.1	129.2	78.6	50.6

	Per capita GRP	males			females		
		1	2	3	1	2	3
Pskov Region	313156	406.3	322.9	83.4	157.8	104.2	53.6
Sevastopol	309115	303.3	216.3	87	120.4	66.3	54.1
Republic of Mari El	298989	404.3	335.3	69	120.7	88.2	32.5
Stavropol Territory	296214	264.2	218	46.2	96.3	59.6	36.7
Kirov Region	292343	346.7	288.2	58.5	110.8	76.4	34.4
Republic of Buryatia	289954	471.4	392.1	79.3	182.5	119.4	63.1
Republic of Adygea (Adygea)	285729	308.3	237.2	71.1	99.1	59	40.1
Kurgan Region	285012	485.8	355.7	130.1	147.2	81.2	66
Chuvash Republic (Chuvashia)	278133	400.9	315.9	85	113.8	81.2	32.6
Altai Territory	270172	416.3	282.7	133.6	145	80.1	64.9
Altai Republic	259944	465.5	386.3	79.2	133	99.1	33.9
Ivanovo Region	254801	383.4	314.2	69.2	134.5	82.8	51.7
Republic of Crimea	248677	353.8	257.8	96	128.1	68.3	59.8
Republic of North Ossetia	248493	269.2	198.1	71.1	78.1	34.3	43.8
Republic of Tyva	243389	642.8	497.2	145.6	287.1	212.4	74.7
Republic of Dagestan	230346	148.1	113.1	35	62.2	30	32.2
Kabardino-Balkarian Republic	197795	203.4	158.2	45.2	83.1	46.1	37
Karachay-Cherkess Republic	196393	246.4	179.4	67	76.3	36.5	39.8

Note: 1 – total avoidable mortality; 2 – mortality from preventable causes (social component); 3 – mortality from treatable causes (medical component). ¹ Excluded: the Nenets autonomous district, the Chechen Republic, and Republic of Ingushetia, due to the lack of or inadequately low indicators, for a considerable number of statistically significant causes.

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